

Electrometric Studies on the Composition and Stability of Nickel Complex of Thiolactic Acid

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Manuscript received 4 May 1971; accepted for publication 9 January 1972

Potentiometric and conductometric studies of the nickel-thiolactic acid system in aqueous 0.1 M NaClO₄ indicate the presence of two complexes; one light brown (1 : 1) predominating at pH 6.5-7.5, and another deep brown (1 : 2) in the pH range 8.0-9.5. The stability constants of these complexes have been determined at three different temperatures by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. The log K values (final) for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes, computed by alternative methods at 20°, 30° and 40°, have been found to be 5.66, 6.03, 6.28 and 7.69, 7.65, 7.52 respectively. The values of overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the reaction have also been evaluated at 30° and found to be -18.19K cal/mole, -9.00K cal/mole and +33.00 cal/degree/mole respectively.

Mercapto-acids and other sulphydryl compounds behave as strong complexing agents owing to the presence of one or more -SH groups for coordination with metal ions, and hence several workers have focussed their attention on the complexation of these compounds with various metals¹⁻⁷. In continuation of our earlier work⁸⁻¹² on the composition, stability constants and thermodynamic functions of metal complexes with thiomalic acid, β -mercapto propionic acid etc, it was considered of interest to extend similar investigations to the complexation of thiolactic acid (referred to herein as TLA) with Ni(II). The literature is, however, silent on the study of Ni²⁺-TLA system and hence the current study has been undertaken. This contribution describes a potentiometric and conductometric study of Ni-TLA system which involved the computation of successive stability constants by alternative methods (correction term method, convergence formulae of successive approximations, least square method), the effect of temperature variation on the stabilities of complexes, and the determination of overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy accompanying the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiolactic acid (98% Evan's chemetics, Inc. New York) and Anal-R (B.D.H.) reagents were used without further purification and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity water. Freshly prepared solutions were always used with a view to avoiding the effects of ageing and hydrolysis. Nickel content in nickel sulphate solution was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoximate.

pH-measurements were made on a Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) pH-meter. A glass electrode of 0-14 pH range, calibrated frequently by using buffers of

different pH values, was used in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by low resistance salt bridge. All the pH titrations were carried out in medium composed of $0.1 M NaClO_4$. The temperatures were controlled by an electrically maintained thermostat (U_8 type German).

The conductance was measured on a Kohlrausch universal bridge using a.f. generator as a source of a.c.

The experimental procedure consists in performing a series of pH and conductometric titrations of thiolactic acid with standard $NaOH$, in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} at various ligand to metal ratios viz., 1 : 1, 2 : 1, 3 : 1. The Calvin and Melchior's¹³ extension of Bjerrum's method¹⁴ was used to calculate the stability constants of the complex formed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction between Ni^{2+} and thiolactic acid was determined by potentiometric and conductometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard alkali.

Fig. 1 represents the pH and conductometric titrations of solutions $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TLA (curves 1 and 5), $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TLA and $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ in $NiSO_4$ (curves 2 and 6), $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TLA and $1.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ in $NiSO_4$ (curves 3 and 7) and $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TLA and $1.11 \times 10^{-3} M NiSO_4$ (curve 4) with $0.1 M NaOH$. The abscissa represents the moles of $NaOH$ added per mole of ligand 'a'.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric (curves 1-4) and Conductometric (curves 5-7) titrations of TLA in absence and presence of Ni^{2+} with $0.1 M NaOH$.

Curves 1 and 5 : $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ TLA.

Curves 2 and 6 : $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ TLA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M NiSO_4$.

Curves 3 and 7 : $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ TLA + $1.66 \times 10^{-3} M NiSO_4$.

Curve 4 : $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ TLA + $1.11 \times 10^{-3} M NiSO_4$.

The appearance of only one inflection, (Fig. 1, curve 1) after one mole of base per mole of ligand has been added, corresponds to the neutralization of the single carboxyl hydrogen. Hence, if free TLA having two replaceable hydrogen ions is denoted as H_2SA , the reaction between 'a' interval of 0-1, may be represented by the equation

The absence of inflection at $a = 2$ indicates that the second proton (sulphydryl) of TLA is not titratable under the experimental conditions.

The addition of equimolar concentration of Ni^{2+} (fig. 1, curve 2) greatly alters the shape of free ligand titration curves as a result of complex formation and consequently a considerable shift in the position of the end point is indicated. Since the extent of the proton displacement depends on the relative affinities of the ligand for hydrogen ion and the metal ions, it is obvious from the curve that the affinity of nickel is not great enough to compete with the relatively high concentration of hydrogen ions in the pH range 3.1-5.0 and consequently Ni^{2+} complex is not appreciably formed in this pH range. Beyond pH 5.0 the affinity of ligand for Ni^{2+} ions increases, as a result of which a considerable lowering in buffer region starts showing finally two inflections at 2 and 3 moles of NaOH per mole of ligand. The inflection at $a = 2$ suggests the formation of $NiSA$ according to equation (2)

Further reaction with another mole of hydroxyl ion is indicated by the fact that the Ni^{2+} titration curve has an additional buffer region and a second inflection at $a = 3$. Thus the second reaction step suggests the formation of a relatively more stable higher complex $Ni(SA)_2^{2-}$ as a result of the disproportionation of 1 : 1 complex with simultaneous precipitation of half of the metal ion in the form of its hydroxide in accordance with the following equation

When two moles of TLA is added to $NiSO_4$ (Fig. 1, curve 3), the curve shows only one inflection at two moles of NaOH per mole of ligand, which corresponds to the formation of $Ni(SA)_2^{2-}$ in accordance with the following equation

Since the significant inflection at 1.5 moles of NaOH per mole of ligand is absent, the formation of $Ni(SA)_2^{2-}$ should occur with considerable overlapping i.e., 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are being formed simultaneously throughout a large portion of the titration. The inflection at 1.66 mole of NaOH per mole of ligand (Fig. 1, curve 4), when the ratio of ligand to metal has increased to 3 : 1. further confirms the formation of overlapping complexes.

Conductometric study : Fig. 1 (curves 5, 6 and 7) represents the changes in conductance when solutions of TLA were titrated against NaOH in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} .

In such conductometric titrations where the weak acid was neutralized by a strong base, the shape of the titration curves depends on the concentration and dissociation constants of the acid. The curves show a minimum, because, when NaOH is added progressively to a solution of TLA, the salt formed during the first part of the reaction tends to suppress the ionization of the acid still present and hence its conductance decreases. The rising salt concentration will, however, tend to increase the conductance, and owing to these opposing influences the titration curves show a minima. As the titration proceeds, a break at $a = 1$ (Fig. 1, curve 5) was obtained beyond which the graph becomes linear.

Fig. 1 (curve 6), for a solution containing 1 : 1 ratio of TLA to Ni^{2+} , shows two breaks at $a = 2$ and 3 corresponding to the formation of NiSA and the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ in accordance with the equations (2) and (3) respectively.

Fig. 1, curve 7, for a solution containing TLA and NiSO_4 in ratio 2 : 1 shows one break at 2 moles of NaOH per mole of ligand which corresponds to the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ in accordance with the equation (4).

These results are similar to those obtained by potentiometric methods demonstrating the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

It may be particularly pointed out that a polynuclear complex is not formed because \bar{n} is a function of $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ only (which has been tested by obtaining measurements of various metal ion concentrations) and is independent of the total metal ion concentration.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} with 0.1 M NaOH at three different temperatures.

Curves 1, 3 and 5 : 3 ml M KNO_3 + 5.0 ml $M/50$ TLA (total volume 30.0 ml) at 20, 30 and 40° respectively.

Curves 2, 4 and 6 : 3.0 ml M KNO_3 + 5.0 ml $M/50$ TLA + 1.0 ml $M/50$ NiSO_4 (total volume 30.0 ml) at 20, 30 and 40° respectively.

Computation of stability constants: Calvin and Melchior's¹³ extension of Bjerrum's¹⁴ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes from potentiometric titration data. The two successive reactions of complex formation may be represented by following equations

The overall stability constant β is given by

$$= \frac{\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}][\text{SA}^{2-}]^2} = K_1 K_2 \quad \dots (8)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the formation constants of the reaction (6) and (7).

The procedure used for calculating the stepwise stability constants of nickel-thiolactate complexes was similar to that adopted in earlier publications⁹⁻¹¹. The evaluation of \bar{n} values were made from Fig. 2 which represents the potentiometric titrations of TLA with standard alkali in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} at three different temperatures. At any $p\text{H}$, the horizontal distances between curves 1-2, 3-4, and 5-6 (corresponding to 20°, 30° and 40° respectively) measures quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of SA^{2-} complexed. This number derived by total Ni^{2+} is \bar{n} . At any $p\text{H}$, $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ was calculated as

$$= \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{SA}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{NiSA}] - 2[\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}]}{\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K a_1 K a_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K a_2} + 1} \quad \dots (9)$$

where $K a_1$ and $K a_2$ are the first and second dissociation constants of the acid¹⁵ (calculated at 20°, 30° and 40°). All quantities in equation (9) are known and thus a series of \bar{n} and $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ values at various $p\text{H}$ were obtained at different temperatures and formation curves were plotted (Fig. 3, curves 1, 2 and 3). The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were read directly from graph at \bar{n} values of 0.5 and 1.5 respectively and were found to be 5.66 and 7.69 (at 20°); 6.03 and 7.65 (at 30°); and 6.28 and 7.52 (at 40°) respectively. These values of successive stability constants were further refined by the following methods

- (1) Convergence formulae of successive approximations¹⁶;
- (2) Correction term method¹⁷;
- (3) Least square method¹⁷;

and shown in table 1.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) on complex formation have been determined at 30°. The expression¹⁷

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta \quad \dots (10)$$

relating overall stability constant to the total free energy change of the reaction was employed for evaluating the value of ΔG , which was found to be -18.19 K.Cal/mole.

Fig. 3. Plot of \bar{m} as a function of $-\log[SA^{2-}]$ at three different temperatures. Curve 1 at 20° , Curve 2 at 30° , Curve 3 at 40° .

The value of ΔH was determined with the help of an isobar equation given as follows

$$d \ln \beta / dT = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2} \quad \dots (11)$$

where T is absolute temperature and R the gas constant and may be more conveniently written in the form¹²

$$d \log \beta / d\left(\frac{i}{T}\right) = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57} \quad \dots (12)$$

The values of $\log \beta$ obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $(1/T)$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point, corresponding to 30° was determined and equated with $-\Delta H/4.57$. The value of ΔH thus determined was found to be 9.0 K.Cal/mole.

After determining the values of ΔG and ΔH , the value of ΔS was obtained by the equation

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T} \text{ and found to be } +33.0 \text{ Cal/degrec/mole.}$$

TABLE 1

Method	20°			30°			40°		
	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log β	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log β	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log β
Convergence formulae	5.35	7.96	13.31	5.93	7.70	13.63	6.24	7.58	13.82
Least square	5.98	7.47	13.45	6.14	7.69	13.83	6.27	7.54	13.81
Correction term	5.66	7.65	13.31	6.02	7.56	13.58	6.35	7.44	13.79
Mean	5.66	7.69	13.35	6.03	7.65	13.68	6.28	7.52	13.80

It is apparent from the above studies that the reaction between Ni^{2+} and TLA results in the formation of two complex species, NiSA and Ni(SA)_2^{2-} . The logarithms of the successive stability constants were found to be 5.66 and 7.69 (at 20°); 6.03 and 7.65 (at 30°) and 6.28 and 7.52 (at 40°) respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS evaluated at 30° were found to be -18.9 K.cal/mole, -9.0 K.cal/mole and $+33.0$ Cal/degree/mole.

The authors thank the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the grant of a research scholarship to one of them (P.S.).

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